

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Pilot trials definition and planning

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is related to Task 7.2 'Pilots trials and validation', which deals with the design of the overall pilot plans, evaluation methodology, analysis and reporting of the Ageing@Work Project. The aim of this deliverable is to set the frame of both pilots and enable each site to plan their use cases and efficiently collect and report data to be share and communicated to consortium members.

The main achievements of this document are:

- To introduce the need for the project, the general framework, the use cases covered per pilot, the connection of the work carried out in this deliverable with the rest of the projects WPs.
- To present the evaluation framework
- To define the pilot plans.
- To define the methodology for the execution of the pilots, including the description of user groups and data related aspects.
- To outline the pilot site management activities in terms of milestones.

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANEFA	Asociación Nacional de Empresarios Fabricantes de Áridos (National Association of Aggregates Manufacturers)
AR	Augmented Reality
DR	Design Requirement
FR	Functional Requirement
IR	Interaction Requirement
R&D	Research & Development
RQ	Research Question
SAG	Siemens
SW	Software
UC	Use Case
UsReq	User Requirement
VR	Virtual Reality
WS	Workshop

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1. Introduction

The European workforce is ageing, by 2030 workers aged 55-64 are expected to make up 30% or more of the workforce. These has led EU governments to raise the official retirement age and restrict possibilities of early retirement, resulting to longer working lives and longer exposure of workers to hazards and risks.

The effects of the ageing workforce also affect EU companies. Industry appears increasingly dependent ton their knowledge, skills and experience of their workers. This pushes companies to explore ways to keep older workers employed for a longer period of time.

The Ageing@Work project focuses on the need to adapt the working conditions of the workers older than 45 years old, to the new needs that arise from their ageing using highly adaptative personalized ICT tool that will help counteract for issues that hinder the ageing workers' workability and well- being . The integrated system will be developed in accordance with a user-centred design process and evaluated in the two pilot sites with regard to core Industry 4.0 processes of mining and machines production.

1.1 Objectives

The objective of the project developed solution is to support the ageing workers to remain healthy, active and productive for longer, anticipating situations of physical and cognitive deterioration, through the fusion of smart working and living environments so that we avoid or delay their appearance as much as possible. This will be based on the use of technological tools, according to the chosen Use Cases, measuring the impact that the use of the A @ W platform has on their lives.

The purpose of this deliverable is to summary the conceptual framework followed in the A@W project to understand current needs of the aging workers. Once the needs of the workers in both pilots have been studied, and the provisional use cases have been built, the proposed framework provide task 7.2 with the necessary tools to systematically demonstrate and evaluate the proposed Ageing@Work tools in realistic conditions with older workers in two pilot sites, focusing on industrial and mining environments. The flexibility of the proposed framework has allowed to adapt the initial pilot plans to the unexpected working conditions due to the pandemic COVID-19 outbreak. In fact, and due to the health crisis caused by the SARS-2 COVID-19 virus, the initial plans to fully develop the pilots in ANEFA and Siemens sites and factories have had to change to adapt to the new security protocols in the pilot sites and to overcome the recruitment barriers derivate from them.

Both in Germany and in Spain, the impact of the virus has led to the establishment of restrictive measures that have particularly affected the freedom of movement of people, which has had repercussions on the organization of work centres, and the measures of security that have been imposed to safeguard the health of the workers. Therefore, it has been necessary to redesign the initial plan, which will be structured in two fundamental blocks:

- On the one hand, the trials of the tools to be physically developed in the mining and industrial operations will remain as originally conceived, but with a smaller number of workers.
- On the other, a new group of participants from the two pilots was planned to assess the solutions from their teleworking settings , who will test the proposed tools.

In both cases, the participants will assess the solutions and their outcomes will be measured using the same evaluation protocol, hence the same questionnaires.

At the end, the evaluation will provide evidence and valuable information on how technology can help the productivity of aging workers, improving data on the effects of ICT tools for accompany people in the natural ageing process, before their retirement. A holistic approach will be adopted, since the analysis will not only include older workers, but also those in charge of their safety and health, as well as younger workers, who after all, they will be the aging workers of the future, so that the results of our research are effective in the medium and long term.

In summary, there is more than one objective that is framed within the main objective of the Pilots, and they are the following:

- Measure the user experience through the direct use of the tools, and through the information obtained, introduce improvements in the system.
- Continuously collect and analyse data that is collected from all relevant sources, that is, through direct measurements, survey results, etc.
- Evaluate the impact that the platform has on the productivity of older workers.
- Evaluate the impact that the platform has on the quality of life of workers.

1.2 Overarching evaluation targets

The general evaluation objectives are those that are present throughout the project regardless of the pilot in which the tests are carried out. They are those that we have to satisfy and respond to, reaching the criteria of success.

This general evaluation framework will be discussed in **Chapter 2** of this deliverable.

Improvements will be sought in the following indicators:

- Improvement in the indicators related to job satisfaction.
- Improvement in the indicators related to the welfare and quality of life of the user.
- Improvement in the indicators related to productivity at work.
- Benefits and added value derived from the tools proposed in the A @ W.

1.3 Use Cases coverage per Pilot Site

The pilots will take place in Spain and Germany. The Spanish pilot will be tested in companies dedicated to the extraction of aggregates, quarries and Spanish gravel pits, which are part of the

National Association of Aggregate Manufacturers-ANEFA; while the German pilot will take place in Siemens's factories and remote offices located in Germany.

The aggregates companies that will participate in this pilot are located in the outskirts of Madrid. Due to the COVID-19 restriction Siemens will focus on a lab factory in Munich and remote office workers from different Siemens sites. However, the number of participants still allow to give a qualitative analysis.¹ Further details about the places where the recruitment of the participants and the evaluation of the solutions will be carried out are included in Chapter 3 of this deliverable.

The original plan on use cases articulated on deliverable D 2.1 (ADD NAME HERE), included the realization of 7 use cases distributed between the Spanish and German pilots, among which were the following:

- **Use Case 1:** Check-list platform
- **Use Case 2:** Communication of absences and vacations
- **Use Case 3.** Musculoskeletal problems.
- **Use Case 4:** Early detection of stress and insomnia, analysis of causes and control.
- **Use Case 5:** Knowledge exchange platform.
- **Use Case 6:** Emergency button.

Given the change of scenery that has occurred after the health crisis caused by the COVID-19, and taking into account the comments or recommendations received from the European Commission on October 30, 2020, about the 7.2 proposal of the Pilot Plans:

- *"Overall, the project takes a direction that is too ambitious. The project should keep focus on one reference solution / pilot and demonstrate"*
- *"The project needs to focus for a feasible relevant solution ready to be implemented in real setting in a realistic time frame. The project should target in the very next phase on a fully focused pilot specification (selection of tools, functionalities, with just 1 avatar and 1 working environment simple) and demonstrate how the project concept works."*

The use cases have been reformulated into the following:

Use Case 1: Virtual Coach and Worker Dashboard: Each of the workers will have a personal coach profile, that represents a virtual representation of the worker, that will support worker on the healthy habits acquisition and monitoring his well-being. In addition, the participant receives feedback from the virtual coach based on their daily monitored activities, health and work authority recommendations, and reference values. Through the dashboard, the personal goals assessment is shown using an easy-to understand visual traffic light and motivational feedback. This gives participants a fast and detailed overview of their current lifestyle status.

¹ REF Flick, U. (2018). *Designing qualitative research*. Sage.

Self-assessment questionnaires and tools are offered in the dashboard to maintain workability and healthy workplace style.

Use Case 2: AR / VR Tools & Knowledge Exchange Platform: Virtual reality learning tools provide the necessary framework for more experienced workers to create a virtual reality tutorial and load it into the application. On the other hand, less experienced workers can download a tutorial and train at home with a virtual reality headset or at the workplace with an augmented reality headset. In addition, the learning tools can provide training sessions for more experienced workers on new machines that they may need to learn to use.

The augmented reality platform aims to help workers in distance training. The platform consists of two communication applications intended to be used by a remote supervisor (located, for example, at home) and a worker in the workplace, and uses intuitive digital instructions that enrich the physical environment of the workplace, thus facilitating the execution of tasks.

The knowledge exchange platform is a web interface that provides two-way access to the knowledge base and supports workers in the manufacturing process, allowing them to interact, collect and share relevant knowledge, ideas and good practice.

Use Case 3: Job Scheduling Tool: The platform is designed as a web application for managers. Different aspects of the organization are available, such as an overview of the organization's daily, weekly and monthly tasks, an overview of the workforce and their skills. Task assignment is supported by a background DSS that helps the manager to distribute the tasks and can reschedule the tasks assigned to the workforce after a change, for example when a day off is requested.

Accordingly with the new description of the Use cases the pilots finally will be performed as it shown in table X:

Site	Pilot description	Use cases to validate
Spain	Quarries	UC1
Germany	Munich industry	UC2
Germany	Remote office	UC3

In addition, Siemens's pilot will try to organize a small-scale pilot of the UC1.

1.4 Relation to other activities and deliverables

This deliverable is the second step in WP7 'Ageing@Work platform integration and validation', and it was initially conceived to be developed from month 12 to month 24. Due to COVID-19 and the consequent difficulties derived from the pandemic that have had to be faced by the

consortium partners, the initial calendar has experimented some adaptations. In this sense, this task will be developed from month 30 to month 40. It will provide the basis to task 7.3 'Pilot Trials and execution', and task 7.4 'Consolidated evaluation of the Ageing@Work platform'. It is also essential for the completion of the rest of the project's WPs to verify the functionalities of the tools.

Pilots are carried out in WP7, but they are inter-related and connected with other activities. The evaluation framework will define the dimensions, the indicators and outline the practical pilot plans for all pilot sites. In addition, it will enable technological teams (WPs 4, 5, 6 and 7) to gather feedback for improving their work and the additions to existing technologies.

The identified Use Cases in WP2 will form the basis for preparing the application and evaluation scenarios so the main findings will also feed the work involved in the creation of the business cases and scenarios and will be disseminated to different stakeholder groups. Training activities will be carried out before any evaluation activities take place.

Figure 1: List of related WPS

	WP Name	WP Leader
WP1	Ethics requirements	CERTH
WP2	User requirements, system specification and architecture	ASER
WP3	Worker and workplace models and orchestration support tools	UPAT
WP4	Unobtrusive ambient activity and behavior tracking	KUL
WP5	The Ageing@Work Virtual Coach	CERTH
WP6	Personalized age-friendly productivity enhancement tools	UPAT
WP7	Ageing@Work platform integration and validation	UPM
WP8	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Business Planning	Q-PLAN
WP9	Project Coordination and Management	CERTH

Table 1: List of WP and WP leader

1.5 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows: the evaluation framework is presented in Chapter 2; Chapter 3 defines the pilot plans in terms of the evaluation dimensions and resulting evaluation targets; The methodology for the execution of the pilots, the study design, the selected indicators per evaluation dimension and data-related aspects are discussed in Chapter 4; Chapter 5 looks at pilot site management activities in terms of milestones and plans and training of participants.

1.6 Challenges

The adoption of technologies at work and home has achieved higher acceptance than did 10 years ago, especially for the older populations. However, there are several challenges when organizing and monitoring such studies, especially in the cases where the technologies have to be installed/integrated and frequent maintenance might be required. For this reason, the evaluation and development teams should closely collaborate in order to be able to foresee any issues and resolve them before use. The Pilots conduction entails multi-group efforts that are efficiently co-ordinated and implemented.

In addition, we continue to be immersed in the terrible effects of the pandemic SARS COV-2-COVID 19 that has shaken the world, leaving millions of people infected and deceased. Our way of life and of relating to each other has changed substantially, and perhaps forever.

In this sense, the project has experienced enormous difficulties in moving forward and it has been especially in the pilots that have seen the need to develop an implementation plan that takes into account constantly changing circumstances, the need to prevent contagions and to ensure the safety of workers who participate as volunteers in the study.

Therefore, what was initially designed as a direct implementation plan in quarries and factories with a lot of face-to-face intervention, must be redesigned towards a more telematic intervention system.

Despite the change of course, this new scenario will allow the project to reach more sites to the extent that we will no longer have the impediments to travel to workplaces, being able to extend the study to more sites and in this way achieving a broader vision.

Another important impediment that must be taken into account is that workers can be reluctant to new technologies, especially the elderly. To avoid this situation, training and awareness work will be very important. Another issue to take into account is the necessary collaboration of the people in charge of running the mining sites and factories.

In this regard, efforts should be made to transmit the objectives that the project is intended to achieve and the benefits that could be obtained both for the health of the workers, making them more efficient for longer, and for the smooth running of the business.

2. Evaluation framework

This A@W evaluation framework is a longitudinal evaluation framework for a 6-month evaluation of using ICT solutions targeting working and non-working daily activities. The framework is based on a collaborative action research approach aimed to early involve the key stakeholders from the beginning of the process. It is characterized by a dynamic user-centred approach, involving throughout the data collection process other people such as business owners, managers, laboratory technicians, health and safety experts, so that a broader overview can be achieved.

The evaluation framework represents the foundation on which the pilot plans will be based on, allowing the iterative discovering of worker's output on four different dimensions. The dimensions are the following:

- Measurement of the tool's **feasibility, acceptance, and usability** by the worker and employers.
- Effects of tools on **workability** conditions.
- Effects of the tools on **productivity**.
- Effects of the tools on the state of **health and general well-being** at work of the worker.

The adaptability of the evaluation framework, the early involvement of the stakeholders from the beginning, and the multidimensional and mixed methodology, can identify and incorporate into the evaluation the differences in the nature of the industrial activities developed in each pilot, the different relationship that workers may have with ICT solutions in each country, and even the differences when it comes to relating to technology in their homes and in their workplace, not only for evaluation purposes, but also in relation to the learning and training process.

3. Pilot Plans

This section covers practical and operational aspects of the pilot execution, once the Ageing@Work system is ready to be deployed in the pilot site (M30). The overall methodology follows in every of the pilots, and user centred design approach implemented using a mix method methodology.

3.1 Overview of pilot sites

This section presents the characteristics of the two pilot sites (Spain and Germany) and the pilot organization and management.

3.1.1 Spanish pilot

The Spanish pilot, organized by ANEFA with the technical support of the UPM, will involve workers from different companies dedicated to the extraction of aggregates and other materials, equipment for the crushing of materials and tapes for the transport and deposit among other equipment. The pilot will involve every of the workers involved in the process, from workers of the quarries, handling heavy machinery, control and security tasks, management and laboratory, and other such as business owners, managers, health and safety managers, factory directors, laboratory managers.

The pilot will take place in two measurement periods preceded by a `pre-pilot` phase that will take place between July and August 2021. A relatively long `pre-pilot` period is established, since in view of the dates on which the It will take place during holiday periods, so in this way we ensure that the recruitment, learning and training process can be carried out with all involved workers.

This `pre-pilot` phase will be structured as follows:

- July participants recruitment and baseline evaluation
- August to assess solution performing and bugs fixing, learning and training.

Full pilot will start in September during a 6-month period. The Spanish pilot users will be selected among workers of the extractive sector who fill the inclusion criteria. The widest possible variety of professional profiles and backgrounds will be sought, so as to obtain the widest possible database.

User profiles and facilities

Participants in the pilot will be workers belong to the company Materiales y Hormigones, SA-MAHORSA, who carry out their work in two production centres, specifically, in the San Martín de la Vega Gravel Pit, where siliceous aggregates are extracted by direct pulling-out, and in the Morata de Tajuña quarry, where limestone aggregate is extracted through drilling and blasting.

In addition, in both centres there are numerous auxiliary services, such as a workshop, warehouse, laboratory (only in the quarry), wastewater treatment plant, scale, offices, changing room and dining room.

For the development of the mining activity several large mobile machines are used, such as tippers or dumpers, loaders, hydraulic excavators, and bulldozers; and fixed machinery, such as the treatment plant itself where extracted rock is processed and classified into different granulometries.

The workers who will be part of the pilot occupy different positions, from machine driver to manager, including office workers and various plant and laboratory operators. All of them have compulsory basic training, except the facultative directors and the Administrative, with a higher academic training.

3.1.2 Siemens Pilot

The German pilot, organized by Siemens, with the technical support of CERTH, will involve SIEMENS (office) workers current working remotely and Portofliomanagers in the Munich factory, all of them over 55 years old. Like the Spanish pilot, the Siemens pilot will have a 'pre-pilot' phase planned between July and August 2021.

Full pilots will start in September. The Siemens UC1 users will be selected randomly between office workers.

UC2 pilot users will also be selected randomly, as the usage of the Pilot is a prerequisite to be allowed to enter the lab factory. As the lab is used by a wide variety of workers from different departments and units, we will reach a very wide spectrum of users. Additionally, we will also involve persons that are already familiar with the lab.

3.2 Use cases objectives and solutions

As it was presented previously, the use cases and objectives for each of them are summarized in the following table:

Module	Objective	Intervention
Virtual Coach and Dashboard	Provide workers with the tools and mechanisms that accompany them in the successful ageing process, to maintain their workability and quality of life while they age	The answers of the baseline assessment are used to create a personal coach profile for the participant. The participant receives feedback from the coach based on their daily monitored activities, health and work authority recommendations, and reference values. Through the dashboard, the personal goals assessment is shown using an easy-to-understand visual traffic light and motivational feedback. This gives participants a fast and detailed overview of their current lifestyle status. Self-assessment questionnaires and tools are offered in the dashboard to maintain workability and healthy workplace style
AR/VR tools and Knowledge Exchange Platform	Enhance and maintain ageing workers' engagement while promoting long-life training and adaptation of working environments and intergenerational knowledge sharing	<p>An XR training solution and a Knowledge Exchange Platform (KEP) will be provided to the SIEMENS pilot to facilitate the interaction and transfer of knowledge from more experienced (possibly older) workers to less experienced (new) workers.</p> <p>The AR Remote Collaboration Tool is an augmented reality platform, aiming to assist workers in remote collaboration and training. The platform consists of two communicating apps intended to be used by a remote supervisor (located e.g., at home) and an on-site worker, and uses tele-presence along with intuitive digital annotations that enrich the physical environment of the workplace, thereby facilitating the execution of on-site tasks and promoting collaboration efficiency, productivity and life-long training.</p>
Job Scheduling Tools	Prevent the lack of communication between managers and workers and facilitate daily workers management and job position adaptations	The manager is provided with job scheduling tools in the form of the participatory work orchestration platform, where s/he can define the workers assignments. The platform is capable to provide recommendations to the manager for upcoming job schedules, which take into account parameters related to the job requirements, along with characteristics and requests of the workers. The platform also provides a direct communication mean between the workers and the manager, as the workers can send through their mobile app, requests such as day-off related ones, to the manager and receive through the platform request outcomes, as well as up-to-date information regarding the job schedule.

Table 2: Use cases-objectives and intervention level

An initial clustering of use case categories per Pilot site follows in the Table below.

Service/application	Germany	Spain
Virtual Coach	✓	✓
Worker Dashboard	✓	✓
AR Tools	✓	
VR Tools	✓	
Knowledge Exchange Platform	✓	
Job Scheduling Tool	✓	✓

Table 3: Use cases per pilot

3.3. Study design

The proposed framework proposes a quasi-experimental two-armed (experimental and control groups) that will be conducted with recurrent measures (baseline, intermediate at 3 months and final at 6 months study. Table 4 represent the final user allocation). The two study conditions are: 1) experiment group that use the Ageing@Work solutions, 2) control group that work as usually done with current working conditions.

3.3.1 Participants and recruitment

The recruitment is planned to start at July 2021. Each pilot site will use existing networks and collaborations to recruit participants established already from the beginning of the project.

General inclusion and exclusion criteria for all the pilot activities is described below. As different activities, different tools, different user groups are addressed at each pilot site, only the basic and common criteria are presented.

- Workers over 55 years old (45 in case of working arrangements that allow early retirement due to special hard-working conditions)
- Without severe health or mental conditions (diagnosis of severe physical or mental condition or disability).
- Speaking and writing skills in Spanish, German.

In addition, following conditions will be taken into account during recruitment in order to facilitate training and pilot deployment:

- The workers will be selected among those workers who have a basic knowledge of new technologies. It will be taken into account that they have a smartphone, a computer or a tablet.
- It will be a factor to take into account that they have ever used any of the existing health or training apps in the market. The objective of not starting from scratch in terms of new technologies is to improve the chances of successful implementation of A@W solutions, so that it is not a strange element in their lives or suppose for them overexertion of learning.
- Finally, it will be taken into account that the subject has a positive attitude, a good predisposition and desire to participate in the project, with enthusiasm about the objectives and improvements that could result in their day-to-day life. The idea is that with this project workers can work longer in optimal conditions, so this is the message that subjects must internalize and want to achieve by participating in the project as potential users.

Once participants were assigned to one of the study arms, an evaluator, independently from the pilot personnel, will administrated the initial questionnaires (VUM questionnaires) to create the personal virtual coach in case of experimental group. The same questionnaires will be administrated to the control group in other to compare at baseline the two arms and avoid bias.

Pilots	Experimental group	Control group
ANEFA	25	25
Siemens	13	13

Table 4: Number of participants per pilot

3.3.2 Ethical approval, supervision and consent to participate

Prior to any testing, partners have to submit their ethics research protocol to AGEING@WORK Ethics Board and the regional committee. All participants abide to the European and National regulations and legislation. The following aspects are addressed and cover the conduction of the AGEING@WORK pilots:

- Privacy protection and confidentiality.
- Informed consent.
- Incidental findings.
- Transparency of the collected data management by the final system and during its

The participants must have given his/her consent prior to the study in order for the personal data collected to be processed and stored by the members of the consortium. Before the employee gives his or her consent, the person concerned will of course be informed of the objectives of the project, the lines of action, the instruments used and the treatment of his or her personal data, always respecting national and European law. The consent must be signed.

In order to supervise the ethical regulation during the whole piloting phase, regulatory authorities on local, national or international level, regulating a wide range of aspects from device safety and essential performance, via legal, ethical and privacy related issues, will revise every of the process through the Ageing@Work Ethics Board with external expertise and

local ethical committees with representatives from all the pilot sites for ensuring that applicable regulations are respected.

In addition, Health and safety committees or teams of ANEFA and Siemens, which will receive periodic reports about the good progress of the project, the solutions implemented, and the results observed, so that they can make a continuous risk assessment.

Pilot	Recruitment status	Ethics approval status
Spanish pilot	Recruitment started from different quarries in the Region. Segmentation will start in M24	Ongoing
German pilot	Recruiting started from different (office) departments for UC1 / UC2. .	Ongoing

Table 5: Recruitment and ethical approval status per pilot

3.3.3 Data management

Before starting any type of activity for the implementation of the pilots, during the pre-pilot phase both those company owners and the study participants will receive an informed consent in which they will be informed of the objectives of the project, the type of study to be carried out, the type of data that will be collected, the type of action that will be required of the user.

Pilot sites will receive only anonymised and coded information. Any recorded data will be available to pilot sites only in anonymised format.

3.3.4 Outcomes

During the piloting phase, a set of validated questionnaires have been selected to measure specific outcomes in the pilot participants.

- *Self-perceived quality of life*, compared to current status and working conditions, enables better outcomes in terms of work life engagement or return to work after severe disease, measured by the SF-12 questionnaire, the short version of SF-36 Health Survey questionnaire, one of the most reliable and widely used quality of life questionnaires. The SF-12 has proved to be a psychometrically robust and practical instrument for use in outcome evaluation of subjective health. The questionnaire consists of 12-items assessing two composite (physical and mental) and eight subdimensions of quality of life: physical functioning, physical role limitation, body pain, general health, vitality, social functioning, emotional role limitation and mental health. In addition to the individual scores of each of the dimensions, a physical and mental health summary can be calculated. The lower the resulting summary score, the lower self-reported health functioning.
- *Work-related wellbeing and psychosocial conditions at work*: The enhancement of working conditions, favouring workers' motivation and productivity, The COPSOQ is designed as a tool for workplace psychosocial risk assessment and for organizational development. It is a generic tool, which can be used for all kinds of jobs that assess different domains. The short version of the questionnaire will be used in this case (work engagement, job satisfaction, job commitment, etc).
- *Technology acceptance*. The Unified Theory on Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)^[1] is a model in the study of technology adoption that integrates eight theories of technology adoption and provides a comprehensive view of the factors affecting users' adoption behaviour. The model presents 4 main dimensions (i.e., effort expectancy, performance expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions), but other dimensions can be added^[2]. Responders are asked to indicate how they perceive their actions towards the technology in different situations using a 7-point Likert scale from 1 to 7 (1=strongly disagree, 7=strongly agree).
- *Other measures*: Other measurements include socio-demographic variables and technology usage logs. The following socio-demographic variables will be collected: Gender, year of birth, educational level. Technology usage logs include number of access, time of use, date of use, number of unexpected, fails, or problems. Other relevant health-related variables will be assessed, specifically if the users have a major change in their life during the experiment duration (i.e., move to another workplace, medical load, etc.)

3.3.3. Procedure

In order to facilitate pilot deployment, outcomes data collection and final data analysis, similar scheduling will be followed in the pilots. The pre-piloting phase will start in June, and it will support technical testing of the solutions in real settings, hence discover bugs or miss working before real pilot start. In addition, it will be a first contact with the technology and training preparation for the involved workers so avoid learning curves that can comprise pilot engagement. Real pilot is planned from September, and they have 6 months duration. An intermediate evaluation is planned at month 3.

Pre-pilot 2021			First Pilot Phase 2021			Interm. Ev. 2021	Second Pilot Phase 2022			Final ev. 2022
June	July	Aug.	Sep.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.	Feb	March	April

Table 6: Pilot's timeline 1

While the UC1 has a strong impact on well-being at work of the participants, the UC2 and UC3 only aims to evaluate the usefulness of the solution for the specific tasks these workers perform during the day. Taking into account this, and as numerous studies in the field of usability testing show, only 4-5 test persons are necessary to uncover 80% of the weak points in a given demonstrator. After that, only those weaknesses that have already been found and uncovered accumulate, the UC2 and UC3 will be only evaluated from the point of view of the usability and feasibility.

The following table presents the measurements instruments for each outcome category.

Questionnaire	At pilot start	At 3 months	At 6 months (if they continue)
Experimental group			
VUM questionnaire	X (only for UC1)		
Basic sociodemo info	X (only for UC2 and UC3)		
SF-12	X (UC1 and UC3)	X (UC1 and UC3)	X (UC1 and UC3)
COPSOQ	X (UC1, UC3, UC2)	X (UC1, UC3, UC2)	X (UC1, UC3, UC2)
UTAUT		X (UC1, UC3, UC2)	X (UC1, UC3, UC2)
Control group			
Basic sociodemo info	X (for the 3 Ucs)		
SF-12	X (UC1 and UC3)	X (UC1 and UC3)	X (UC1 and UC3)
COPSOQ	X (UC1, UC3, UC2)	X (UC1, UC3, UC2)	X (UC1, UC3, UC2)

Table 7: Outcomes, measurement instruments and assessment timeline

3.3.4 Monitoring

Each pilot site appointed one or more pilot site managers that will be responsible for communicating with the Consortium partners the status, problems, risks and issues at each pilot site. This manager oversees the conduction of pilots and is responsible for obtaining ethics approval and also for applying the AGEING@WORK ethics policy to their site. In addition, if there are any updates in related legislation and guidelines, they have to inform the AGEING@WORK ethics committee.

The following table presents the names of the responsible people at each pilot site:

Pilot Site	Site Manager
ANEFA	Rosa Carretón Moreno María Loeck de Lapuerta
SIEMENS	Fritjof Kaiser Ginger Claassen Markus Dubielzig

Table 8: Site manager per pilot

4. Services/tools per pilot site

In order to ensure the correct performing of the deployed solutions and avoid problems that compromise the evaluation of the solutions, a set of preparation and validation and verification activities are planned, before, during and after pilot activities.

4.1 Validation and verification activities

These activities will be carried out as a result of the collaboration between the technical integrators (i.e., teams responsible for the services) and the teams that will develop and support the Ageing@Work platform. These activities will take place to ensure that the services are working properly and their integration to the Ageing@Work platform is successful, with no problems and time delays. Any issues and bugs should be rectified before testing starts.

Technical partners have agreed an integration plan that minimize the deployment problems, but also allow the continuous monitoring of the solutions working, so early detect problems and implement the necessary measurements to solve them.

4.2. Training activities

Training activities is a fundamental part of the pilot preparation, so avoid excessive learning curves and/or discover resistance to change barriers that comprise the pilot results. Training activities will be carried out before any testing takes place, during the pre-pilot phase. Training will be carried out only for the services that the development and evaluation teams in collaboration decide that training is necessary.

It is important that the researchers involved in communicating and interacting with participants to be trained not only in using the services, the tools and the Ageing@Work platform but to be trained on how to communicate with ageing workers.

The contents of the training sessions will be prepared so that the end user can learn to use the devices and tools in the least number of sessions possible. Physical and remote demonstrations will be carried out by the responsible teams.

In addition, learning content and clear written instructions will be prepared so that they are easily accessible by the user if he needs them during the learning process and also during the use process. Direct communication channels will be set up with the pilot's managers so that the end user can raise any doubts or problems that may arise during the use of the devices and tools.

Internal communication channels will also be established between those responsible for the pilot and the technical partners to resolve doubts or problems during the training and installation phase as well as during the use phase.

4.3 Automatic data collection from the Ageing@Work system

Apart from the participants outcomes, collected within the study methodology, the Ageing@Work system automatically collects a set of logs and data that should be handled properly according to the national and international laws. This section presents the specific methodology to ensure data privacy and data management in each of the proposed solutions.

4.3.1 Methodology on data collection Ageing@Work mobile application

In order to collect data with the Ageing@Work application, the workers must provide their consent and enable the Activity & Location Tracking Service. If this service is enabled, the workers will be aware since a non-cancellable notification is created for as long as the service is running. While this service is running, activity & location-related data are being recorded.

In order to populate the Virtual coach, and perform the necessary adaptations of their profiles, workers are also prompted to answer some demographic questions and health/mood-related questionnaires, which when answered are sent to the server. Furthermore, if the users have enabled the provided keyboard, keystroke timing sequences are being stored. Moreover, if the users have installed Google Fit and Samsung Health and they have provided their consent to those 3rd party applications, the system will also retrieve data from those. Finally, the new available data will be sent to the server periodically and if WiFi is available.

Analysis and treatment & about what will be the procedure to treat the data:

Machine learning models might be developed in order to estimate the predictive capabilities of the system, based on the data and the ground truths (questionnaires) being collected. The analysed data will be anonymous.

How it will be stored and who will be responsible for its treatment and management:

The mobile application is communicating with the server using the HTTPS protocol. Any request requires an access token, provided after user's login, for safety. The data are stored within a dedicated secure server within CERTH, under the supervision of CERTH's employees, who are also participating to the Ageing@Work project. Sensitive personal information such as exact location tracking information is not stored in the server.

How will they be interpreted, what will be the indicators of success, etc:

Moreover, the predictive capabilities of the machine learning models will be another indicator of success. (e.g., using features from activities & location the system manages to predict participants' personality traits scores or binarization [extrovert vs introvert]) Finally, the outcomes of the questionnaires before and after the use of the application (e.g.,

increase of participant's rating to the workability, or lower levels of stress), as well as participant's rating for the application will be another indicator of success.

4.3.2 Methodology of data collection on Workers Dashboard

Worker dashboard collects information from a set self-perceived workability assessment, as well as a set of data to personalize goals and feedback. This data will be stored locally and do not be shared with other applications. In addition, worker access log to the different solution will be collected. The Worker dashboard makes use of data that have been collected by other means within the Ageing@Work data collection framework and are being made available in the wVUM.

Analysis and treatment & about what will be the procedure to treat the data:

Used data are input through the worker interface and are not of a statistical nature. No additional treatment is expected

How it will be stored and who will be responsible for its treatment and management:

The data are stored within a dedicated secure server within CERTH, under the supervision of CERTH's employees, and the support of UPM.

How will they be interpreted, what will be the indicators of success, etc:

The data will be interpreted to deliver the personalized motivational messages and provide historical information about the self-perceived workability.

4.3.3 Methodology of data collection: job scheduling tool

The data used by the participatory work orchestration tool will be collected in the Ageing@Work manager platform. The manager will be responsible for inputting the data, which consist of the definition of facility shifts, tasks to be performed at each shift, and skills required to complete each task. This data will be collected through the web interface, using intuitive forms with relevant fields. In addition, the manager will be able to edit the data that has been input in order to correct errors or alter schedule parameters.

In addition, the Participatory Work Orchestration Tool makes use of data that have been collected by other means within the Ageing@Work data collection framework and are being made available in the wVUM. The Participatory Work Orchestration Tool performs no immediate data collection actions.

Analysis and treatment & about what will be the procedure to treat the data:

Used data are input through the manager interface and are not of a statistical nature, as such they are expected to be free of outliers and other unwanted artifacts. A basic string manipulation to ensure constant character properties will be performed.

How it will be stored and who will be responsible for its treatment and management:

The data are stored within a dedicated secure server within CERTH, under the supervision of CERTH's employees, who are also participating to the Ageing@Work project.

How will they be interpreted, what will be the indicators of success, etc:

The data will be interpreted to formulate shift schedules in accordance with objectives and constraints stipulated as part of the overall facility schedule, and as part of the worker interaction with the Ageing@Work components. Said constraints will be derived by the algorithm using shift, task and skill data derived through the input of the managers in the Ageing@Work manager platform.

4.3.4 Methodology of data collection on AR remote collaboration apps

Methodology of data collection:

In order to collect data with the AR Remote Collaboration applications the users must provide their consent and enable the device camera access and microphone service. While the apps are running, data logs related to the actions of the users inside the apps are stored. Those logs include login timestamps, call sessions between users and the type of actions performed.

Analysis and treatment & about what will be the procedure to treat the data:

The collected data will be first pre-processed for cleaning, meaning that methods to remove outliers will be employed and for feature extraction. Finally, machine learning models might be developed in order to improve the capabilities of the system, based on the data. The analysed data will be anonymous.

How it will be stored and who will be responsible for its treatment and management:

The AR Remote Guide and Worker applications are communicating with the server using the HTTPS protocol. Any request requires an access token, provided after user's login, for safety. The data are stored within a dedicated secure server within CERTH, under the supervision of CERTH's employees, who are also participating to the Ageing@Workproject.

How will they be interpreted, what will be the indicators of success, etc:

The statistical analysis outcomes will be an initial indicator of good performance. To claim success though the number of participants has to be as large as possible (the least would be 50 users).

The participant's rating for the applications through the Google Play Store rating system as well as the call quality rating within the AR Remote Guide app will be another indicator of success.

5. Management and monitoring of the pilots

The pilots are organized in such a way that there is clear identification of each pilot site in terms of identified milestones, and programmes for recruitment, training and briefing of end user participants. Monthly meeting will be planned in order to update status, data collection process, detected risks and suggested mitigation steps, problems and next step. A common template will be provided in order to have appropriate follow up of the pilots.

5.1. Sustaining the feedback loops

The pilot site managers will be responsible to communicate any issues with the services and/or the platform directly to the responsible technical and architecture teams. Issues will be categorised to **imminent** (have to be solved immediately), to **secondary** (can wait for the end of the month), to tertiary (they can wait) and finally to **optional** (not important but nice to have).

5.2. Communication Strategy and Timeline

To ensure smooth operation and communication among pilot managers and other WP teams, any related issues with regards to delays and problems will be discussed. In addition, the common templates will allow for harmonising the data communication, analysis and reporting.

6. Conclusion and next steps

This document presents the evaluation framework overall plans for the Ageing@Work pilots. The targets to be reached serve the main dimensions and the framework. Despite the different tools that will be tested at each pilot site, the pilot sites share the same objective and overall aim, to investigate how an overall ICT system can improve ageing workers general well-being, helping help them to be productive for longer.

The specific questionnaires addressing the evaluation of services are made specific in the annexes.

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ANNEX 1: Questionnaires

PARTICIPANT GENERAL INFORMATION

This section will be filled by the assigned researcher.

DATE: _____

PARTICIPANT ID: _____

(Be sure you include the unique ID assigned to each of the participant at the beginning of the project)

Evaluation period: Baseline
 Intermediate (3 months)
 Final (6 months)

Instructions

This is the complete version of the questionnaires for the Ageing@Work system evaluation. The evaluation process is composed of 3 periods plus an initial questionnaire to build the personal Worker Virtual Model.

Following table presents the periods each of the questionnaires should be administered.

Construct	Questionnaire	S	T0	T1	T2
Health and working conditions questionnaire	Socio-demographic data and virtual coach data	X			
Quality of life	SF-12		X	X	X
Work related well-being and psychosocial conditions at work	COPSOQ		X	X	X
Technology acceptance	UTAUT			X	X

Health and working conditions questionnaire Instructions

Administration information. This questionnaire is a self-administrated questionnaire that should be administrated at in the recruitment process if the participant fills the inclusion criteria. The objective of the project is to provide the basic information required to contextualize the participant and create his/her personal virtual model.

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

1. Where do you live? _____

Ageing@Work

GA #826299

Floor: _____

2. Where do you work? _____

Address : _____ Floor: _____

3. Gender: 1 Male 2 Female

4. Are you: 1 Single 2 In relationship or Married 3 Divorced / Separated 4 Widowed

5. How long have you been involved in the present work tasks? _____

6. What is the title of your main paid job/occupation? _____

7. A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total monthly income, is your household able to make ends meet...?

1 Very easily 2 Easily 3 Fairly easily
4 With some difficulty 5 With difficulty 6 With great difficulty

8. Are you, in your household, the person who contributes the most to the household income?

1 Yes 2 No 3 All equally

9. In general, how often are you involved in any of the following activities outside work?

a. Caring for and/or educating your children, grandchildren

1 Daily 2 Several times a week 3 Several times a month
4 Less often 5 Never 6 Not applicable

b. Caring for elderly/disabled relatives

1 Daily 2 Several times a week 3 Several times a month
4 Less often 5 Never 6 Not applicable

HEALTH AND CAPABILITIES

1. Assume that your work ability at its best have a value of 10 points. How many points would you give your **current work ability**? (0 means that you currently cannot work at all)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Cannot work									Best ever
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2. Assume that your job performance at its best has a value of 10 points. How many points would you give your **current job performance**?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Very poor									Excellent

3. **How much do you move and exert yourself physically during your leisure time?**

If your activity varies greatly between, for example, summer and winter, try to estimate an average. The question refers to the past year.

Mark only one option!

Physically inactive

Almost completely inactive, reading, watching television, watching movies, using computers or doing other sedentary activities, during leisure time 1

Some light physical activity

Physically active for at least 4 hours/week, such as riding a bicycle or walking to work, walking with the family, gardening, fishing, table tennis, bowling etc. 2

Regular physical activity and training

Spending time doing heavy gardening, running, swimming, playing tennis, badminton, calisthenics and similar activities, for at least 2-3 hours/week. 3

Regular hard physical training for competitive sports

Spending time running, orienteering, skiing, swimming, playing football, handball etc. several times per week 4

4. How do you spend your leisure time apart from physical activity? Add a number from 1 (favourite activity) to 5 (least favourite activity)

___ Restaurant/Pub/Cafeteria/Bar Which one ? _____

___ Museum/monument/cinema/theatre/exhibition Which one ? _____

___ Shop Which one ? _____

___ Gym/stadium/court/sports centre/park Which one ? _____

___ Meeting with friends or relatives at a home (home leisure activities) Which one ?

5. How often do you go to a Restaurant/Pub/Cafeteria/Bar?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Never	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Everyday
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6. How often do you go to museum/monument/cinema/theatre/exhibition?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Never	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Everyday
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7. How often do you shop?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Never	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Everyday
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8. How often do you go to gym/stadium/court/sports centre/park?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Never	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Everyday
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9. Do you smoke / use tobacco? 1 YES 2 NO

10. How many portions of fruits and vegetables do you eat per day? (A portion of fruit or vegetables is 80g. e.g., 1 medium sized piece of fruit; 1 dessert bowl of salad; a large handful of berries or grapes; 2 broccoli spears; 3 heaped tablespoons of peas, carrots or sweetcorn)

_____ portions / day

11. How many alcoholic drinks do you usually have each week? _____

(Standard drink: Beer: 1 can (373ml); Wine: 1 medium glass (125ml) Port or sherry: 1 small glass (60ml) Spirits/liqueur: 1 nip (30ml)

12. What is an average amount of water you drink per day?
 ____ liter(s)

13. In general, I would say my health is:
 5 Excellent 4 Very good 3 Good 2 Fair 1 Poor

14. I have problems with vision: 1 YES (check below) 2 NO
 If YES: 1 Near 2 Far 3 I am colour-blind 4 Other (please describe)

15. If an answer to the question 10 is yes, my vision with correction glasses/lenses is:
 1 Excellent 2 Good 3 Moderate 4 Poor

16. I have problem with hearing: 1 YES 2 NO

17. I have a history of seizures: 1 YES 2 NO

18. I have problem with lifting my arms: 1 YES 2 NO

How easily do you get dizzy or lose concentration?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Extremely
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19.

20. If an answer to the question 12 is YES, my hearing with hearing aid is:
 1 Excellent 2 Good 3 Moderate 4 Poor

21. In your opinion, are you able to:

a. Run a half kilometre? 1 Without difficulty 2 With difficulty or unable

b. Walk two kilometres? 1 Without difficulty 2 With difficulty or unable

c. Climb several flight or stairs? 1 Without difficulty 2 With difficulty or unable

22. In the past 12 months, how many days in total were you absent from work for reasons of health problems?
 _____ days

23. Do you have any illness or health problem which has lasted, or is expected to last, for more than 6 months?

1 YES 2 NO

24. Over the last 12 months, did you have any of the following health problems?

- a. backache 1 YES 2 NO
- b. muscular pains in shoulders, neck and/or upper limbs 1 YES 2 NO
- c. muscular pains in lower limbs (hips, legs, knees, feet etc.) 1 YES 2 NO
- d. overall fatigue 1 YES 2 NO
- e. other (describe)

25. Physical fatigue involves extreme physical tiredness and an inability to engage in physical activity. During the PAST 12 MONTHS, how often did you feel physically exhausted at the end of the workday?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Never	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Everyday
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26. Over the last 6 months, did you experience overall fatigue?

1 YES 2 NO

27. How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Never	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Everyday
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28. How well are you able to concentrate?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Extremely
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29. How well are you able to handle multiple things at the same time?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Extremely
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Not at all										
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30. How satisfied are you with your sleep?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very dissatisfied	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied
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31. **Stress** means the situation when a person feels tense, restless, nervous, or anxious, or is unable to sleep at night because his mind is troubled all the time.
How often have you been stressed during the last 4 weeks?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Never	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Everyday
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32. I am confident in my ability to solve problems that I might face in life
(For example: I can usually handle whatever comes my way, If I try hard enough, I can overcome difficult problems, I can stick to my aims and accomplish my goals)

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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33. How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very dissatisfied	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied
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34. How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very dissatisfied	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied
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35. How often do you socialize with friends / neighbours / relatives?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Never	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Everyday
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36. How would you rate your quality of life?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very poor	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Very good
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37. Do you use any mobile app (Fitbit etc) to measure your daily activities?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	2 <input type="checkbox"/> No
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If yes, which one ones?

WELLBEING AT WORK

1. Do you feel motivated and involved in your work?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Extremely
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2. Regarding your work in general. How pleased are you with your job as a whole, everything taken into consideration?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very dissatisfied	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied
---	----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------------	---

3. Do you feel that your work drains so much of your energy that it has a negative effect on your private life?

1 To a very large extent 2 To a large extent 3 Somewhat
 4 To a small extent 5 To a very small extent

4. How often can you take a break?

Every half an hour Every hour Every 2-4 hours
 Once during a workday Never

5. How long do your breaks last?

6. Do you feel that your work takes so much of your time that it has a negative effect on your private life?

- To a very large extent
 To a large extent
 Somewhat
 To a small extent
 To a very small extent

7. Are you worried about becoming unemployed?

- To a very large extent
 To a large extent
 Somewhat
 To a small extent
 To a very small extent

8. Are you worried about it being difficult for you to find another job if you became unemployed?

- To a very large extent
 To a large extent
 Somewhat
 To a small extent
 To a very small extent

9. In a scale of 1 to 10, meaning 1 very dissatisfied and 10 very satisfied, how would you rate your income?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Mean time to complete task

1) What is your best turnaround time?

2) What is your most likely turnaround time?

3) What is your worst turnaround time?

JOB DEMANDS

1. How physically exerting do you perceive your current work?

1 No exertion	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 Maximum exertion
------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	------------------------

Please indicate, using the following scale, are you exposed at work to ...?

<p>2. Carrying or moving heavy loads</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										
<p>3. Tiring or painful positions (e.g., working with hand lifted, squatting, kneeling)</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										
<p>4. Standing</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										
<p>5. Sitting</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										
<p>6. Repetitive hand or arm movements</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										
<p>7. Vibrations from hand tools, machinery, etc.</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										
<p>8. High temperatures which make you perspire even when not working</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										
<p>9. Low temperatures whether indoors or outdoors</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										
<p>10. From a scale of 1 to 10, how much humidity does the environment of your work have?</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tbody> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 Not at all </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 2 </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 3 </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 4 </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 5 </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 6 </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 7 </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 8 </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 9 </td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> 10 Extremely </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Not at all	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Extremely
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Not at all	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Extremely	
<p>11. Breathing in smoke, fumes (such as welding or exhaust fumes), powder or dust (such as mineral dust) etc.</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>										

<p>12. Handling or being in skin contact with chemical products or substances</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>
<p>13. Breathing in vapours such as solvents and thinners</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>
<p>14. Does your main paid job involve working with computers, laptops, smartphones etc.?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Around $\frac{1}{4}$ of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Never </p>
<p>15. How often do you not have time to complete all your work tasks?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>16. Do you get behind with your work?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>17. Do you work at a high pace throughout the day?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>18. Do you have to work very fast?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>19. Is your work varied?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>20. Do you have to do the same thing over and over again?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>21. Do you feel isolated from colleagues while working?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>

22. Do you have to keep your eyes on lots of things while you work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
23. Does your work require that you remember a lot of things? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
24. Does your work demand that you are good at coming up with new ideas? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
25. Does your work require you to make difficult decisions? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
26. a. How often do you get help and support from your immediate superior, if needed? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
27. How often do you get help and support from your colleagues, if needed? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
28. Have you been involved in quarrels or conflicts at your workplace during the last 12 months? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
29. Do you have a large degree of influence on the decisions concerning your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
30. Do you have the possibility of learning new things through your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
31. Can you use your skills or expertise in your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever

<p>32. Is there space for elderly employees in your company?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent </p>
<p>33. Are you working as an employee or are you self-employed? <input type="checkbox"/> Employee <input type="checkbox"/> Self-employed</p>
<p>34. What kind of employment contract do you have in your main job?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Contract of unlimited duration <input type="checkbox"/> Contract of limited duration <input type="checkbox"/> A temporary employment agency contract <input type="checkbox"/> An apprenticeship or other training scheme <input type="checkbox"/> No contract <input type="checkbox"/> Other (describe): _____ </p>
<p>35. How many hours do you usually work per week in your main paid job? _____</p>
<p>36. During last 12 months, have you worked in more than one location? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
<p>37. Do you always use personal protective equipment when it is required? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
<p>38. Do you trust in emergency/rescue procedures and staff in your company? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
<p>39. Regarding the health and safety risks related to performance of your job, how well informed would you say you are?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Very well informed <input type="checkbox"/> Well informed <input type="checkbox"/> Not very well informed <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all well informed </p>
<p>40. How satisfied are you with your access to health services?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Very unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neither satisfied not unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied </p>
<p>41. Does your employer provide you an additional (private) health insurance? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent </p>
<p>42. Do you have to take stairs at your workplace?</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent </p>

Health and working conditions questionnaire

Dear Participant!

The survey is conducted within the Ageing@Work Project that your company is involved in.

This questionnaire is aimed at assessment of working conditions and their relationship to employees' health. It consists of two main parts: your health status and working conditions.

The survey is anonymous. The individual data will not be available to any of your supervisors.

We encourage you to give your honest opinion!

Personality Traits

„You find yourself as a person that...”

1. Is talkative
1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

2. Tends to find fault with others
1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

3. Does a thorough job
1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

4. Is depressed, blue
1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

5. Comes up with new ideas
1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

6. Is reserved
1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

7. Is helpful and unselfish with others
1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

8. Can be somewhat careless
1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

9. Is relaxed, handles stress well

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

10. Is curious about many different things

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

11. Is full of energy

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

12. Starts quarrels with others

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

13. Is a reliable worker

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

14. Can be tense

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

15. Is ingenious, a deep thinker

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

16. Generates a lot of enthusiasm

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

17. Has a forgiving nature

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

18. Tends to be disorganized

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

19. Worries a lot

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

20. Has an active imagination

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

21. Tends to be quiet

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

22. Is generally trusting

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

23. Tends to be lazy

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

24. Is emotionally stable, not easily upset

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

25. Is inventive

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

26. Has an assertive personality

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

27. Can be cold and aloof

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

28. Perseveres until the task is finished

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

29. Can be

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

moody

30. Values artistic, aesthetic experiences

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

31. Is sometimes shy, inhibited

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

32. Is considerate and kind to almost everyone

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

33. Does things efficiently

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

34. Remains calm in tense situations

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

35. Prefers work that is routine

1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

36. Is outgoing, sociable
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
37. Is sometimes rude to others
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
38. Makes plans and follows through with them
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
39. Get nervous easily
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
40. Likes to reflect, plays with ideas
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
41. Has few artistic interests
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
42. Likes to cooperate with others
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
43. Is easily distracted
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
44. Is sophisticated in art, music or literature
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever

Professional Skills

- 1) Do you have any driving license?
 Truck JCB Bus Car Motorcycle Other
- 2) How often do you manage your time successfully ?
 1 Always 2 Often 3 Sometimes 4 Seldom 5 Never / hardly ever
- 3) How good are your leadership skills?
 1 Very Poor 2 Poor 3 Intermediate 4 Good 5 Excellent
- 4) How good are your skills in public speaking?

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very Poor 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Poor 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Good 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
5) How would you characterize your flexibility in operations and thinking? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very Poor 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Poor 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Good 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
6) How would you rate your ability to work in teams? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very Poor 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Poor 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Good 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent

Goal

- 1) What would you like to improve at your workplace and home life? (Max 100 words)

Day Routine

- 1) Please provide us with a short description of your day routine (max 100 words)

SF12 HEALTH SURVEY

This survey asks for your views about your health. This information will help keep track of how you feel and how well you are able to do your usual activities. Answer each question by choosing just one answer. If you are unsure how to answer a question, please give the best answer you can.

1. In general, would you say your health is
 1 Excellent 2 Very Good 3 Good 4 Fair 5 Poor

The following two questions are about activities you might do during a typical day. Does YOUR HEALTH NOW LIMIT YOU in these activities? If so, how much?

	Yes, Limited A Lot	Yes, Limited A Little	No, Not Limited at All
2. MODERATE ACTIVITIES, such as moving a table, pushing a vacuum cleaner, bowling, or playing golf:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>
3. Climbing SEVERAL flights of stairs:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>

During the PAST 4 WEEKS have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular activities AS A RESULT OF YOUR PHYSICAL HEALTH?

	Yes	No
4. ACCOMPLISHED LESS than you would like:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>
5. Were limited in the KIND of work or other activities:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>

During the PAST 4 WEEKS, were you limited in the kind of work you do or other regular activities AS A RESULT OF ANY EMOTIONAL PROBLEMS (such as feeling depressed or anxious)?

	Yes	No
6. ACCOMPLISHED LESS than you would like:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>
7. Didn't do work or other activities as CAREFULLY as usual:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>

8. During the PAST 4 WEEKS, how much did PAIN interfere with your normal work (including both work outside the home and housework)?
 1 Not at All 2 A Little Bit 3 Moderately 4 Quite a Bit 5 Extremely

The next three questions are about how you feel and how things have been DURING THE PAST 4 WEEKS. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling. How much of the time during the PAST 4 WEEKS –

	All of the Time	Most of the Time	A Good Bit of the Time	Some of the Time	A Little of the Time	None of the Time
9. Have you felt calm and peaceful?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>
10. Did you have a lot of energy?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>
11. Have you felt downhearted and blue?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>
12. During the PAST 4 WEEKS, how much of the time has your PHYSICAL HEALTH OR	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>

EMOTIONAL PROBLEMS interfered with your social activities (like visiting with friends, relatives, etc.)?							
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

COPSOQ (short version) Work related well-being

This survey asks for your views about your psychosocial conditions and health promotion in your work. This information will help keep track of how you feel in your work and collect important information to prompt preventive actions. Answer each question by choosing just one answer. If you are unsure how to answer a question, please give the best answer you can.

Quantitative Demands
1. Do you have to work very fast? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never/hardly ever
2. Is your workload unevenly distributed so it piles up? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never/hardly ever
3. How often do you have time to complete all your tasks? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never/hardly ever
Emotional Demands
4. Does your work put you in emotionally disturbing situations? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
5. Do you get emotionally involved in your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
Demands for Hiding Emotions
6. Does your work require that you hide your feelings? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
Influence at Work
7. Do you have a large degree of influence concerning your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
8. Can you influence the amount of work assigned to you? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
9. Do you have any influence on what you do at work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
Possibilities for Development

<p>10. Does your work require you to take the initiative?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>11. Do you have the possibility of learning new things through your work?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>Degree of Freedom at Work</p>
<p>12. Can you decide when to take a break?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever</p>
<p>Meaning of Work</p>
<p>13. Is your work meaningful?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>14. Do you feel that the work you do is important?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>Commitment to the Workplace</p>
<p>15. Would you like to stay at your current place of work for the rest of your working life?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>16. Do you feel that your place of work is of great personal importance to you?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>Predictability</p>
<p>17. At your place of work, are you informed well in advance concerning for example important decisions, changes, or plans for the future?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>18. Do you receive all the information you need in order to your work well?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>Quality of Leadership</p>
<p>19. To what extent would you say that your immediate superior ...</p> <p>a. Is good at work planning?</p>

<p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent </p> <p>b. Is good at solving conflicts?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent </p>
Social Support
<p>20. How often do you get help and support from your colleagues?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>21. How often do you get help and support from your immediate superior?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
Feedback at Work
<p>22. How often does your superior talk with you about how well you carry out your work?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>23. How often do your colleagues talk with you about how well you carry out your work?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
Sense of Community
<p>24. Is there good co-operation between you and your colleagues?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
<p>25. Do you feel part of a community at your place of work?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever </p>
Insecurity at Work
<p>26. Are you worried about...?</p> <p>a. Becoming unemployed? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>b. New technology making you redundant? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>c. being difficult for you to find another job if you become unemployed? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>d. Being transferred to another job against your will? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
Job Satisfaction
<p>27. Regarding your work in general. How pleased are you with...?</p> <p>a. Your work prospects? <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Highly unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant</p> <p>b. The physical working conditions? <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Highly unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant</p> <p>c. The way your abilities are used? <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Highly unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant</p> <p>d. Your job as a whole, everything taken into consideration? <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Highly unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant</p>

General Health

28. In general, would you say your health is

- Always
 Often
 Sometimes
 Seldom
 Never / hardly ever

Mental Health

 29. These questions are about how you feel and how things have been with you during the past 4 weeks. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling. How much of the time during the past 4 weeks ²–

a. Have you ever been a very nervous person?

- All of the time
 Most of the time
 Some of the time
 A little of the time
 None of the time

b. Have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?

- All of the time
 Most of the time
 Some of the time
 A little of the time
 None of the time

c. Have you been a happy person?

- All of the time
 Most of the time
 Some of the time
 A little of the time
 None of the time

Vitality³

30. These questions are about how you feel and how things have been with you during the past 4 weeks. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling. How much of the time during the past 4 weeks –

a. Did you feel full of pep?

- All of the time
 Most of the time
 Some of the time
 A little of the time
 None of the time

b. Did you feel worn out?

- All of the time
 Most of the time
 Some of the time
 A little of the time
 None of the time

c. Did you feel tired?

- All of the time
 Most of the time
 Some of the time
 A little of the time
 None of the time

UTAUT Acceptability of the solution

This survey asks for your views about the technology you have used. This information will help keep track your intention to use the technology and possible acceptance

² This domain also includes Have you felt calm and peaceful? And Have you felt downhearted and blue? The questions are also in SF-12 and should be added in this section to complete the evaluation

³ This domain also includes the question Did you have a lot of energy? That is in the SF-12 to evaluate add the appropriate answer her

barriers. Answer each question by choosing just one answer. If you are unsure how to answer a question, please give the best answer you can.

Effort Expectancy							
	Fully disagree	Disagree	Some-what disagree	Nor agree, nor disagree	Some What agree	Agree	Fully agree
EE1: My interaction with the system is clear and understandable	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
EE2 It is easy for me to become skilful at using the system	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
I find the system easy to use	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
Learning to operate the system is easy to me	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
Performance expectancy							
	Fully disagree	Disagree	Some-what disagree	Nor agree, nor disagree	Some What agree	Agree	Fully agree
PE1: I find the system useful for my purposes (daily living/job)	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
PE2: Using the system enables me to accomplish task more quickly.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
PE3: Using the system increases my productivity	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
PE4: If I use the system, I will increase my chances of getting better quality of life	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
Social influence							
	Fully disagree	Disagree	Some-what disagree	Nor agree, nor disagree	Some What agree	Agree	Fully agree
SI1: People who influence my behaviour think that I should use the system	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
SI2: People who are important to me think that I should use the system.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
SI3: Management would motivate to use of the system	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
Facilitating conditions							
	Fully disagree	Disagree	Some-what disagree	Nor agree, nor disagree	Some What agree	Agree	Fully agree
FC1: I have the resources necessary to use the IoT device	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
FC2: I have the knowledge necessary to use the system.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
FC3: The system is not compatible with other systems I use during my working hours	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
FC4: A specific person (or group) is available for assistance with the system difficulties.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>

